

Hardware and embedded algorithms for real time variable rate fertiliser applications

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Abstract

Efficient use of fertilisers, in particular the use of Nitrogen (N), is one of the rate-limiting factors in meeting global food production requirements. While N is a key driver in increasing crop yields, overuse can also lead to negative environmental and health impacts. It has been suggested that Variable Rate Fertiliser (VRF) techniques may help to reduce excessive N applications. VRF seeks to spatially vary fertiliser input based on estimated crop requirements, however a major challenge in the operational deployment of VRF systems is the automated processing of large amounts of sensor data in real-time. Machine learning (ML) techniques have shown promise in their ability to process these large, high-velocity data streams, and to produce accurate predictions. This paper will use a simulation testing methodology on real hardware to compare two existing ML algorithms and a prototype implementation of a newly developed algorithm for their applicability to VRF application.

Background

Low-powered hardware

In order to develop a dedicated hardware device such as a VRF controller, it would be ideal to use small form factor and low powered hardware. This is due to power consumption and physical space concerns, as there may not be a reliable source of power (e.g. mounted on a spray boom), nor convenient mounting locations. One of the challenges with using such hardware is that it is generally very limited in computational resources such as memory and CPU power (Ibrahim, 2006). This is especially apparent when designing systems using microcontrollers, but can be somewhat avoided by making use of Single Board Computer (SBC) designs. SBC's integrate a System on Chip (SoC) with on-board peripherals, external communication interfaces, permanent storage, and extra memory. A popular choice for SoC designs today is the ARM architecture, due to its simple core design and ease of manufacture (Ryzhyk, 2006). The commercially available TS-7400v2 has 256MB of memory and a low power consumption (1.2W typical, <10mW low power sleep) (Technologic Systems, 2014). Other development boards exist with higher memory and CPU capabilities, however power usage also increases on such systems (Asadi et al., 2014), and the primary focus for this paper is low power devices. These systems can be configured to operate either as "bare metal" Real-Time Operating Systems (RTOS), or can make use of a dedicated kernel such as Linux.

Variable-rate fertiliser / nitrogen prediction

Currently, growers use one of several techniques, including the SIX EASY STEPS in order to reduce the excess N application to crops, while still maintaining yields (Schroeder et al., 2005, Skocaj et al., 2012). These processes however require time and effort on behalf of the growers in order to be effective. Technological alternatives for estimating N requirements include active optical reflectance sensors mounted on vehicles or low-level aircraft (Lamb et al., 2014, Lamb et al., 2011, Trotter et al., 2010), as well as the use of satellite imagery, aerial multispectral, and ground based field spectroscopy (Robson et al., 2016). A key challenge in developing a dedicated VRF system is the possibility of incorrect or faulty software causing irreversible damage to expensive fertiliser delivery equipment, similar to numerous incidents in other industries (Astigarraga et al. 2010).

Machine-learning techniques

The use of ML techniques has been shown to provide useful and accurate predictions from high-bandwidth data streams in various Precision Agriculture areas such as irrigation control (Capraro et al. 2008), robotic vision (Sadgrove et al., 2017), and yield prediction (Pantazi et al., 2016). Use of ML techniques for VRF applications requires good performance in both time and accuracy. Poor algorithm performance potentially incurs economic and ecological losses, particularly for airborne delivery methods due to the high speed of aircraft, which is typically 55 to 65 ms⁻¹ for fertiliser application in the widely used Air Tractor AT-502B (Air Tractor, 2017).

ML algorithms used in precision agriculture today include Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) (Behmann et al., 2015). This paper will focus on backpropagation ANN, and C-Support Vector Classifiers (C-SVC). An implementation of a newly developed ML algorithm designed to help alleviate the challenges of the embedded system environment, and meet the rigorous requirements imposed by VRF applications (Cohen, 2016) will also be presented.

Input-processing output

Many of the current Precision Agriculture solutions can be generalised as a standard Input-Processing-Output (IPO) model (Figure 1) commonly found in software development. This model has also been used extensively in the automotive computing industry (Goel, 2010). For VRF application, ML techniques will be used as the Processing stage, and a variety of sensors are available to use as the Input stage including optical indices (e.g. NDVI, REIP), and soil apparent electrical conductivity (ECa).

Figure 1. Input-processing-output model in precision agriculture. Note this model encompasses a range of embedded applications including the VRF controller.

Methods

Data overview

The data used in this paper consists of measurements taken from an 18Ha field of Z30 stage wheat in Warialda, NSW using a quad bike fitted with two commercially available sensors. Red Edge Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (RNDVI) was captured using a Holland Scientific Crop Circle™ ACS211 red edge (670nm) sensor (Holland Scientific, 2011), and Soil Apparent Electrical Conductivity (ECa) was captured using a Geonics EM38-MK2 (Geonics, 2013) unit operating in vertical dipole mode.

A total of 2399 data instances were captured and geo-referenced using a Trimble TSCe Ranger data logger with a connected DGPS device (Trimble Navigation Ltd, 2002). An agronomic expert was on-site during data collection to determine the classification labels (fertiliser / no fertiliser) of each data instance. Due to the nature of the data, there was an imbalance in the classification labels, where 699 locations were classified as positive (fertiliser required), and 1700 classified as negative (no fertiliser required). In order to compensate for this imbalance, an upsampling strategy was employed for both training and testing sets (Ganganwar, 2012), and min-max normalisation of values to the [-1:1] range was performed in order to avoid the effect of features being measured on different quantitative scales (Flach, 2012).

Testing ML techniques using simulation testing

In order to effectively and efficiently develop hardware systems for precision agriculture, and VRF in particular, it would be ideal to have offline testing capabilities so that physical access to a sensor or output actuator is not required. An effective way to model and verify embedded system behaviour is through simulation testing (Billington et al., 2010). This involves recreating, as close as possible, the environmental conditions of the system as it was during the data capture. To do this, timestamped data samples must be captured during the collection phase. Data logging devices have been used in the automotive industry for decades (Bell, 1982), and data logging, playback, and visualisation devices are widely available. While there are many data logging devices available for the agricultural sector, there is a lack of playback devices suitable for simulation testing, therefore a custom device is required. A simple data playback logger was created using the Teensy 3.6, a 32-bit USB Development board which provides connectivity of sensors through various system protocols such as I2C, SPI, and UART (PJRC, 2017). This device allows capture of timestamped data streams to built-in storage (microSD) at a rate adjustable by the user during setup. It also has the ability to replay the data back into the System Under Test (SUT), either at the same rate as was originally captured or at a rate dictated by the SUT. For this paper, the existing data set was loaded into the device for replay to the ML simulation testing hardware.

Fuzzy box

The Fuzzy Box (FB) technique is a binary classification algorithm designed with real-time embedded systems in mind to provide fast and accurate predictions with minimal computational overhead (Cohen, 2016). It was developed to compliment the Dynamic Aerial Survey project which showed that it was possible to use existing machine-learning techniques in an offline setting for VRF prediction (Falzon et al., 2012). FB is trained by taking the data from each input feature (sensor) and dividing the value range into bins. The split points for these bins are calculated based on the range of the training set values, and can either be done by percentile of the instances which fall into each bin (percentile boxing), or by evenly splitting the feature value range (even boxing). This process is repeated for each number of bins required from S_{MIN} to S_{MAX}. The ratio of positive/negative training samples is saved as the prior ratio.

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for each feature as ft:
  for S := S_min -> S_max:
    for i := 1 -> S+1:
      if even:
        split[i] = ft.min + (i+1)*(ft.max - ft.min)/(S+1)
      if percentile:
        split[i] = percentile(ft.values, (i+1)/(S+1)*100)
  
```

Calculating fuzzy box split points

Once the split points have been calculated, boxes are then created by using each feature as a separate dimension. Each n-dimensional box is assigned a rational number to keep track of how many training instances fall into this box, and how many of those have a positive classification. Figure 2 demonstrates a model with 2 features at 10 splits. The model can be updated without requiring all of the previous training data, which allows for the possibility of online training at minimal computational cost.

Figure 2. Fuzzy box model for 2 features using 10 splits, showing percentile boxing (left) and even boxing (right)

The total number of bins created for the model can be calculated from the equation, where f is the number of input features and S is the number of split points. This directly corresponds to the memory requirement for the model. Due to the exponential nature of this equation, the memory requirement grows beyond the scope of both embedded systems and modern computers rather quickly. The Fuzzy Box model is designed for use with only with a small number of input features (data streams). The feature limit is 7 for a reasonably low number of splits (10) using 2x16bit values before running into the 256MB limit commonly used on SBC's. Equations 1 and 2 show the memory requirements for a model using 32-bit boxes with 7 and 8 features respectively.

$\sum_{S=1}^{10} (S + 1)^7 = 37\,567\,596 \text{ boxes} \equiv 143.3 \text{ MiB} \quad (1)$	$\sum_{S=1}^{10} (S + 1)^8 = 382\,090\,214 \text{ boxes} \equiv 1.42 \text{ GiB} \quad (2)$
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In order to make a prediction on an incoming instance, the value of each feature is compared to the model's split points, thus placing that instance in one of the model's boxes. The corresponding ratios for that box are read, and the mean of all such boxes (one for each value of S) is found. This gives a rational value which can be compared to the prior ratio and a prediction can be made according to Equation 3.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} + & \text{if } x \geq \text{prior} \\ - & \text{if } x < \text{prior} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

An implementation of FB has been developed in the Python language, with the intention of writing an optimised implementation in C for embedded systems if the algorithm shows promise. For this reason, FB is being compared against highly optimised libraries in order to measure the potential viability for VRF applications.

Metrics for choosing an ML technique for VRF

For this paper, the primary concern is in comparing performance metrics for prediction time of ML algorithms in a simulated environment, as training is usually done offline before the controller is deployed. For future hardware devices however, it would be ideal to use a learning strategy which allows for online training of the prediction model without requiring the previous training data. A comparison was made against two commonly used ML techniques; an ANN using backpropagation, and a C-SVC with Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. Existing software libraries were used for the ANN (FANN) (Nissen, 2003) and C-SVC (LIBSVM) (Chang and Lin, 2011). Timing performance was measured by recording the time taken to train the model, and the average time taken for classification prediction.

Timing metrics were taken using a low-powered development board (Raspberry Pi with Broadcom BCM2837@1.2GHz), and a high-powered modern system (MacBook Pro 2015 with Intel Core i7 @ 2.2GHz), and were averaged over 100 executions of the simulation code. Note that due to differing CPU architectures (ARM vs. x86), clock speed is not directly related to the performance of the processor. Spatial resolution of each algorithm was calculated as the time taken for an aircraft travelling 60ms⁻¹ to make a single prediction on the BCM2837. In order to provide a fair comparison between the algorithms, a grid search over the hyper-parameter value ranges was performed, and

model accuracy was assessed using stratified 10-fold cross-validation. (Kohavi, 1995). Worst-case time and space complexity for each model is compared (Table 4) in order to show how resource requirements grow as features are added.

The Fuzzy Box algorithm complexity was calculated directly from the implementation code

Another consideration when comparing algorithms is the ability to retrain the model 'on-the-fly', which would become a key factor for VRF controllers providing a site-to-site self-calibration mechanism. Assuming training data can be collected with classification labels, online training of each of these algorithms is certainly possible, however ANN's and SVC's were not originally designed for retraining, and specialised implementations are usually used (Heinen and Engel, 2010), while the FB algorithm was designed with incremental training in mind (Cohen, 2016).

Results

Table 1. Parameter values for ML training

ANN Parameter Selection			C-SVC Parameter Selection	
Internal Activation Function	SIGMOID		C	2048
Output Activation Function	BINARY STEP		Gamma	0.0078125
# Hidden Layers	7			
Learning Rate	0.007			

Table 2. Computation time results (average over 100 executions)

	Training Time (ms)		Prediction Time (s)		Spatial Resolution (BCM2837)
	BCM2837 @1.2GHz	Intel Core i7 @2.2GHz	BCM2837 @1.2GHz	Intel Core i7 @ 2.2GHz	
ANN	12449.45	846.46	16.64	2.09	1.0mm
C-SVC	786.56	97.88	261.72	19.76	15.7mm
Fuzzy Box₍₅₎ (even)	513.88	64.88	112.64	15.87	6.8mm
Fuzzy Box₍₅₎ (percentile)	670.95	82.76	108.6	16.00	6.5mm
Fuzzy Box₍₁₀₎ (even)	1038.44	130.89	234.16	32.27	14.1mm
Fuzzy Box₍₁₀₎ (percentile)	1606.43	182.30	218.64	30.69	13.1mm

Table 3. Model testing results

	Accuracy	Precision	F ₁ Score	Gmean
ANN	85.37	83.33	76.21	84.08
C-SVC	85.77	83.56	76.06	83.38
Fuzzy Box₍₅₎ (even)	84.85	78.55	86.36	84.13
Fuzzy Box₍₅₎ (percentile)	85.88	85.88	85.88	85.88
Fuzzy Box₍₁₀₎ (even)	84.85	78.42	86.39	84.09
Fuzzy Box₍₁₀₎ (percentile)	86.47	85.43	86.67	86.46

Table 4. Worst-case model training complexity (n=features, m=training instances, c=box splits)

	Space complexity	Time complexity
ANN	$O(n^2)$ ^[1]	$O(n^2)$ ^[1]
C-SVC	$O(m^2)$ ^[2]	$O(m^3)$ ^[2]
Fuzzy Box	$O(c^n)$	$O(n)$

^[1] (Owechko and Shams, 1994), ^[2] (Tsang et al., 2005)

Discussion

Successful testing of time and accuracy metrics was performed on three ML algorithms against a real-world data set using a simulation of the data collection. It was found that prediction times using an ANN were significantly faster than both the C-SVC and FB algorithms, however this comes at the cost of lower F1-score, meaning a generally less robust classifier when both the positive ("fertiliser required"), and negative ("no fertiliser required") predictions are the primary concern. The FB algorithm shows promise as an accurate classifier for VRF application, scoring marginally higher in all prediction metrics when using the percentile boxing method. When using the even boxing method, FB still performs comparably to the ANN and C-SVC, and although is less precise when making "fertiliser required" predictions, it has a similarly high F1 score. This implies that FB will perform best as a general classifier regardless of whether applying fertiliser or not applying fertiliser are the most important factors. This decision could range from site to site and so it is important that both are considered.

It can be seen from the spatial resolution calculations, that even the slowest prediction algorithm (C-SVC), has a spatial resolution high enough to make it suitable for VRF application when used on the industry-standard Air Tractor AT-502B aircraft. Since online training is a potential goal for a ML-based VRF controller, it is necessary to consider training time complexity. Table 4 shows that the training time for FB grows linearly with features, while ANN's and C-SVC's grow exponentially. In practical terms, this means that more input sensors can be processed by the VRF system when using FB. However, the FB memory requirements grow large very fast and depend on both number of features, and number of box splits. Therefore, by keeping the number of splits low, the memory requirements become manageable, and as the results show, accuracy and precision are still high even when going down to 5 splits.

Conclusion

Testing of ML models in a simulated environment shows promising results and is a reliable way to test software for an embedded device such as a VRF controller without requiring access to the physical sensor equipment. In the future, modelling and verification of complete system behaviour including the output stage of the IPO model can be undertaken using simulation driven development. There is also more room for timing improvements of the FB algorithm by optimising the code implementation.

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